

OS Awards

European Public Recognition Scheme for Open Source SW/HW Initiatives

D3.2: Open Source Indicator Design and Policy Recommendations

Lead Partner:	RISE
Version:	1.0
Status:	Submitted to EC
Dissemination Level:	PU
Document Link:	

Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable report presents initial outputs from the OSAwards.eu project, which aims to enable Europe's strategic digital autonomy through tighter integration of Open Source Software and Hardware. By developing a system of annual awards and a comprehensive framework for measuring adoption, impact, and sustainability, the project establishes multi-level indicators based on GitHub activity, classical innovation metrics, and stakeholder engagement with funding bodies. Early findings highlight adoption growth and core sustainability challenges in security, maintenance, and innovation, producing candidate metrics for use in policy, evaluation, and tool development. The next project phase will further validate these indicators through stakeholder focus groups and quantitative analysis on country and organisational levels, leading to a unified assessment model for European open source technologies.

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DOCUMENT LOG

V0.1	Document structure and formatting	Johan Linåker (RISE)
V0.2	Added text in section 2,3,4	Peter Neuhäusler (Fraunhofer ISI), Denilton Luiz Darold (Fraunhofer ISI), Knut Blind (Fraunhofer ISI)
V0.3	Added text on T3.3	Johan Linåker (RISE)
V0.4	Addressed internal review comments	Johan Linåker (RISE), Peter Neuhäusler (Fraunhofer ISI)
V0.5	Revision based on internal review	Johan Linåker (RISE)
V1.0	Submitted final version	

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OS Awards.EU is funded by the European Commission, Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101189668 (CSA). The information and views set out in this deliverable are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. The information in this document is provided “as is”, and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any specific purpose. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein. The OS Awards.EU Consortium members shall have no liability for damages of any kind including without limitation direct, special, indirect, or consequential damages that may result from the use of these materials subject to any liability which is mandatory due to applicable law.

TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
EC	European Commission
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OSH	Open Source Hardware

OSS	Open Source Software
PC	Project Coordinator
PO	Project Office
TF	Task Force
TI	Thematic Initiatives
TM	Technical Manager
MS	Member State
WP	Work Package

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Executive summary

The OS Awards.eu project, a Horizon-funded Coordination and Support Action, seeks to strengthen Europe’s digital competitiveness and strategic autonomy by fostering skills, recognition, and innovation in Open Source Software (OSS) and Open Source Hardware (OSH). As global supply chains and technological dependencies evolve, Europe must reinforce its capabilities in open source technologies. By establishing a European awards system and defining robust metrics for open source adoption, impact, and sustainability, the project aims to highlight exemplary initiatives and inform future policy and funding decisions. The report presents initial outputs from two key tasks: deriving indicators of open source adoption and impact (T3.2), and indicators of open source sustainability (T3.3).

The work on adoption and impact focuses on developing a multi-dimensional framework based on both classical innovation indicators—such as patents, publications, and company data—and digital activity metrics drawn primarily from GitHub. Using the Fraunhofer ISI GitHub Data Collector, the project has generated country- and organisation-level datasets encompassing indicators like repositories, forks, stars, commits, and contributors. Complementing these activity-based datasets, traditional innovation indicators from PATSTAT, Scopus, and Crunchbase provide context on how open source technologies contribute to scientific and commercial innovation. Findings reveal strong growth in open source activity until 2020, but also limitations in available metadata, emphasising the need for further validation and integration of these indicators into European digital performance measures.

The sustainability analysis (T3.3) complements this quantitative work through a qualitative, iterative research design engaging major open source funders, initiatives, and ecosystem actors across Europe and internationally. Insights from 25 expert interviews identify security, maintenance, and innovation potential as top sustainability concerns for OSS and OSH projects. Emerging candidate metrics are organised into dimensions of prevalence, activity, robustness, and maturity, reflecting engagement, responsiveness, dependency structure, and best practices—particularly in security and governance. The results underscore the value of sustainability metrics both for guiding funders’ decision-making and for supporting long-term digital resilience in Europe.

Together, the two tasks establish a foundation for a unified indicator model capable of measuring open source’s adoption, impact, and sustainability at multiple levels—project, organisation, country, and ecosystem. These metrics will inform the OS Awards.eu visualisation tool (T3.4) and support the policy, evaluation, and recognition frameworks envisioned by the project. The next phase will involve validating indicators through focus groups at the European Open Source Week and subsequent quantitative trace-data analysis, culminating in refined, open-access metrics and policy recommendations in the project’s final deliverable (D3.2).

Introduction

Open Source Software (OSS) and Open Source Hardware (OSH) make up critical levers for enabling Europe’s digital future, competitiveness, and strategic autonomy. Yet, awareness, knowledge, and culture are lacking across many parts of society. There is a need to increasing Europe’s skills and capabilities related to OSS and OSH for the continent’s technology industry to keep pace with global competition. As geopolitics keep on influencing relationships and supply-chains in the digital world, there is further need for Europe to increase its influence and control of its digital infrastructure and wider sphere of interest.

To support Europe’s growth of skills and capabilities to leverage OSS and OSH accordingly, the OS Awards.eu project, a Horizon-funded Coordination and Support Action (CSA), is establishing a system of European annual awards that can act as a lighthouse to encourage increased contribution to, integration of, and exploitation of open source assets. This report presents a deliverable in the context of this work, looking to enable measurement and follow-up of the impact open source technology has on the European economy and the sustainability of open source technology on which Europe depends.

The objective of the report is to derive metrics on the 1) adoption and impact, and 2) sustainability of open source (including OSS and OSH) projects respectively. On the one hand, for identifying and characterising potential nominees and custom awards in WP4 and WP5 of the OS Awards.eu project. On the other, for proposing open source metrics in various digital maturity and innovation indices, relating to both public and private sectors, startups, and society at large. Such indices would contribute to sustainable impact of the project assets through exploitation (WP7/WP8) during and far beyond the project’s life cycle.

The work is distributed across two specific tasks, T3.2 focused on deriving indicators of Open Source adoption and impact, and T3.3 focused on deriving indicators of Open Source sustainability

1.1 T3.2 - Indicators of Open Source Adoption & Impact

Within this task, metrics and means of characterising the adoption and impact of critical OS projects in general and in the areas identified as critical per in T3.1 are proposed and developed. The task will develop a comprehensive framework for measuring OS activities and impacts to support the work of the involved stakeholders in carrying out the awards, i.e. by providing indicators to shortlist actors, projects, or organisations. On top of that, and maybe even more important, it will provide aggregate (organisation and/or country) level statistics that serve as a further input into the visualisation tool (T3.4) to inform policy makers and further stakeholders about activities and developments in the OS world. Last but not least, these data and the analyses derived from these data may provide inputs into further media activities within the project.

We have developed adoption and impact indicators from several databases, which can roughly be grouped into two categories: a) “classic” indicators from the innovation research literature like patents, scientific publications and the number of companies within the OS world and b) indicators on OS activities from GitHub. These two indicators complement each other in the sense that the

GitHub indicators are supposed to measure innovation activities in the OS(S) world, however, this has not yet been confirmed empirically. With the data at hand, we not only aim to provide aggregate statistics, but we will also try to validate whether the OS activities indicator measures more than mere “activities” in OS but also innovation in OS. The downside of the GitHub indicator, however, is that we can only assess OSS activities but cannot provide further analyses on OSH. This does not represent a deliberate focus on OSS, it only implies that OSH activities cannot be measured on the basis of this indicator.

Within each indicator category, i.e. the OS activities as well as the innovation measures, indicators for adoption and impact can be derived. As for the adoption part, this mostly entails a count if the outputs within the given indicator categories, i.e. the number of OS repositories or the number of contributors with regards to published OSS or the number of patents or scientific publications. The impact indicators, on the other hand, mostly consist of indicators touching upon the visibility or the quality of these outputs, i.e. how many people share interest in OS repositories, how many citations do patents or publications receive or similar. This means that we cannot categorise one group of indicators as “adoption” vs. “impact” indicators, but we will rather differentiate between “adoption” and “impact” indicators within each indicator category.

1.2 T3.3 - Indicators of Open Source Sustainability

Within this task, metrics and means of characterising the critical components’ sustainability are developed and proposed, e.g., the level to which an OSS or OSH project is maintained over time without interruption or decrease in quality. The sustainability characteristics impact what type of recognition and awards may be most suitable and help to sustain the component. Sustainability metrics further help actors in, e.g., public sector and industry, identify where and what types of policy and support measures may be needed to enable and contribute to a robust and secure digital infrastructure. The target audience includes EU programs (e.g., FOSSEPS), industry initiatives (e.g., OpenSSF), government funding programs (Sovereign TechFund), national government institutions (e.g., through national government OSPOs), and industry (e.g., through industry OSPOs). The task will be directed by the areas identified as critical per in T3.1. This analysis will also be used in WP4/WP5 as input for identifying and characterising potential nominees and custom awards.

To investigate potential metrics and means of characterising the health and sustainability of OSS and OSH components, we take the perspective of funding programs and institutions that sponsor OS technology financially or through other types of support actions. Funding initiatives can be found in a broad range of categories, including public-private partnerships (AlphaOmega), government initiatives (Sovereign Tech Agency), federal initiatives (e.g., NGI), non-profits (NLNet), venture funding (e.g., UNICEF Ventures), single companies (e.g., Indeed, Google, Spotify), and public entities (e.g., City of Munich). Taking the funders’ lens, the task specifically explores what sustainability aspects need to be considered and how, so funders can 1) assess the value or potential value of OSS projects when making funding decisions, 2) assess the sustainability of projects and identify sustainability issues that would benefit from funding, 3) understand and

characterise a project's sustainability needs, and 4) measure the impact of funding on a project's sustainability.

1.3 Initial outputs of deliverable

This report presents research design and initial results from the first iteration of the two tasks T3.2 and T3.3. The final and comprehensive indicator design, and policy recommendations will be provided in the final version of this deliverable (D3.2) in month 24 of the OS Awards.eu project.

2 Methodology

Below, we present the methodological approach for the two tasks (T3.2 and T3.3) within the OS Awards.eu project, which provide the input into this report and the deliverable it represents.

2.1 Indicators of Open Source Impact (T3.2)

For the assessment of OS impact, we have tapped into several data sources to find out which data source provides reliable information for the assessment of open source adoption and impact within Europe. Hereby, we differentiated between “classical” innovation indicators, like patent filings and scientific publications, and more novel indicators based on direct OS activities as measured by GitHub repositories and related indicators. The relevant databases and the methodology of its provision will be outlined below.

Before digging into the data, it should be noted that the area of open source adoption and impact measures is still very new as a research topic and quite difficult to capture in a systematic way. Consequently, some of these indicators still are very experimental and have to be tested with regards to their validity.

2.1.1 OS project information from GitHub

In order to be able to analyse data from GitHub, these data had to be collected from the GitHub repository. In order to do that, Fraunhofer ISI has developed the *GitHub Data Collector*, which is a combination of a GitHub web crawler, and a relational database based on these data. We have published the *GitHub Data Collector* itself as an open source code on GitHub (<https://github.com/maiklovenotwar/github-data-collector>). It is freely accessible, and a full documentation can be found under the above link online. The GitHub Data Collector focuses on:

- Collection of comprehensive GitHub repository data using efficient collection strategies
- Capturing of contributor information, including location data
- Collection of organisational data with metadata and location information
- Geocoding of location data to enrich it with country and regional information
- Storage of all data in an SQLite or MySQL database for external analysis purposes

2.1.2 OS patenting information from PATSTAT

The patent data for the study were extracted from the "EPO Worldwide Patent Statistical Database" (PATSTAT) provided by the European Patent Office. PATSTAT is a relational database, covering information about published patents from more than 80 patent authorities worldwide, dating back to the late 19th century. Within this database, we searched for patents related to OS software, OS hardware as well as OS software and OS hardware licenses. For the demarcation of these groups, a combination of International Patent Classification (IPC) classes and keywords was applied. The IPC classes were used to limit the results to digital technologies in a very broad sense, while the keywords were used for the fine-grained demarcation of OS patents within the realm of

digital technologies. The list of keywords is based on the input of the OS experts within the consortium. For further analyses, patents are counted based on the priority year, i.e. the first available date in the filing process and we focused on transnational patents (EPO filings plus filings through the PCT-route, excluding double counts (Frietsch/Schmoch 2010)).

2.1.3 OS publication information from SCOPUS and Open Alex

The bibliometric data and analyses are based on Elsevier's Scopus database. Scopus contains information on scientific articles published in approximately 16,000 journals worldwide by authors from all over the world. It mainly covers journals in the fields of natural sciences, technology and medicine, but also in the social sciences and humanities. This database enables a detailed analysis of scientific publications and citations for every country in the world. Within this database, we searched for scientific publications (articles, letters, reviews, notes) that write about OS software, OS hardware as well as OS software and OS hardware licenses as for the patent data, we first limited the results to fields of science related to maths, physics and computer science. From there, we used similar keywords as for the patents to identify OS related publications. In addition to the publications that write about open source, we use data from Open Alex to identify publications that were published as open access (green/gold/hybrid). Open Alex indexes more than 250 million publications from more than 250.000 sources with a worldwide coverage.

2.1.4 OS company information from Crunchbase

Crunchbase is a company that collects data on start-ups for investors. Over the years, it has built up an extensive company database that collects and maintains data from companies in many countries and makes it commercially available via a web tool. The Crunchbase database allows users to select sectors, company size categories, financing details, etc. Crunchbase is now considered one of the most reliable company databases, and its selection options are very extensive. However, there are limitations in terms of transparency, i.e. there is little information available about how the data is collected, sorted and evaluated.

For the present analysis, companies that belong to the "Open source" industry group according to Crunchbase's own industry classification were selected. Random checks were also carried out to verify whether these companies are involved in OS according to their business description ('Field description').

2.2 Indicators of Open Source Sustainability (T3.3)

A qualitative and iterative research approach is adopted to investigate potential metrics and means of characterising the health and sustainability of OSS and OSH components. The investigation engages with both European and international funding programs and institutions that sponsor open source technology financially or through other types of support actions.

By adopting a design science research approach, our work aims contextualising identified metrics and means of characterising the health and sustainability, into a model for OSS and OSH funders to structure the selection, evaluation, and follow-up process of their funding, and identify what questions to ask to guide the process. This will also enable a specific use case for the visualisation

tool being developed in T3.4 of the OS Awards.eu project, which this report and underpinning task will provide input to.

The mixed-methods research approach is divided into three iterations: qualitative interview survey, focus groups, and trace-data analysis for metric implementation and evaluation.

2.2.1 Iteration 1: Qualitative interview survey

In a first iteration of the study, a qualitative survey with semi structured interviews have been conducted with funders identified through purposeful sampling (Lenberg et al., 2024). The goal is to create a general understanding on the funders’ goals, process for selecting and evaluating OSS projects, what questions are asked and indicators used, what challenges that are experienced, and what support may be needed to alleviate these challenges.

An interview questionnaire (see Annex A) was used consisting of open-ended questions guided by the overarching study’s research questions. Interviews were conducted online (e.g., through Teams or Zoom), last between 30-60 minutes, and recorded. In all, 25 experts from both funding bodies as well as foundations and projects having received funds have been interviewed (see table 1). Recordings were transcribed locally and offline using an open source AI LLM to enable further analysis, using a thematic analysis approach, a process we are still undergoing. Transcriptions and analysis are shared with interviewees for validation and ensure any sensitive matters are retracted or anonymised per the interviewees’ requests.

Table 1: Overview of interviewees from both funding bodies as well as foundations and projects having received funds.

Funder	Interviewee	Role
Sovereign Tech Agency	Paul Sharratt, Mirko Swillus	Policy and research manager; Program manager
AlphaOmega	Michael Winser	Program director
Prototype Fund	Marie Kreil	Co-Director / Program Management
Mozilla-MOSS	Mehan Jayasuriya	Senior Program Manager
Open Source Technology Improvement Fund	Amir Montazery, Derek Zimmer	Managing director; Founder
Eclipse Foundation	Mike Milinkovich, Mikaël Barello	Executive Director, Head of Security
Internet Security Research Council	Josh Aas, Shannon Robinson	Executive Director; Fund raiser
Microsoft	Emma Irwin	OSPO
Rust Foundation	Rebecca Rumbul	Executive Director & CEO
cURL	Daniel Stenberg	Maintainer

Reproducible-Builds	Chris Lamb	
Chan Zuckerberg Foundation	Dario Taraborelli	Researcher
Drupal Association	Tim Lehnen	CTO
Open Technology Fund	Susan Kennedy	Program manager
Atlantic Council	John Speed Meyers, Stewart Scott	
UNICEF Ventures	Janina Allal	Open Source Innovation Specialist
Google	Mary Radomile	OSPO
Bloomberg	Alyssa Wright	OSPO
Erlang Ecosystem Foundation	Alistair Woodman	Board Member
Indeed	Duane Obrian	OSPO

Findings will be synthesised into a first version of the model and serve as a foundation for the second iteration of the study. Candidate metrics will be shared with T3.4 of the OS Awards.eu project to enable early implementation and evaluation in the planned Visualisation tool.

2.2.2 Iteration 2: Focus groups

In this part, a series of focus groups (Kontio et al., 2008) will help to further evolve and validate the proposed model and underpinning metrics and means for characterising the health and sustainability of OSS and OSH components. All interviewees will be invited along with external experts and members of the broader OSS community, including CHAOSS. An initial physical focus group will be co-located with FOSDEM in Brussels during the European Open Source Week. Additional online focus groups will accommodate different time zones to enable inclusive participation.

Data will be analysed and synthesised iteratively using thematic analysis, where findings from one workshop will feed into the next. Separate workshop reports will be compiled and shared with participants to enable further input and validation.

When the model is considered mature enough, it will be published through an open access report and submitted to a scientific peer-reviewed venue. The refined metrics will be shared with T3.4 of the OS Awards.eu project to enable necessary implementation and evaluation in the planned Visualisation tool.

2.2.3 Iteration 3: Trace-data analysis

In the third and final iteration, trace-data analysis will be performed on the identified metrics. We will explore and compare metrics by OSS/OSH projects and under different funding institutions

and programs. With this more quantitative work, we aim to identify which metrics predict healthy and sustainable outcomes for OSS and OSH projects.

The final results will be published through an open access report and submitted to a scientific peer-reviewed venue. The final metrics will be shared with T3.4 of the OS Awards.eu project to enable necessary implementation and evaluation in the planned Visualisation tool.

3 Initial findings and progress

In this section, we present initial findings on identifying indicators of open source impact, as well as health and sustainability.

3.1 Indicators of Open Source Impact

We have calculated several indicators with regards to measuring OS activities and impact. In this sub-section, we will first of all focus on the GitHub based indicators on OS activities and then turn to the more classical innovation indicators.

3.1.1 Indicators of OS activities

Based on the GitHub Data Collector, Fraunhofer ISI has set-up an SQL database at the level of single GitHub repositories, containing information on all GitHub repositories from 2008 until the end of 2024 that have received at least 5 stars, i.e. we focus on repositories that have at least received some attention from the community, which can serve as a first filter to focus on actually visible/impactful repositories. In addition, this keeps the data handling on an acceptable level. In Table 2, we have summarised the GitHub based indicators that have already been provided to the consortium, which can serve as a basis for the metrics based selection of academy nominees and as a first input to feed into the visualisation tool (Task 3.4). The indicators have been aggregated at the organisational as well as the country level in order to serve that purpose.

Table 2 GitHub based indicators

Variable name	Variable description
<i>Country level</i>	
org_total_organizations.csv	Total number of organizations by country
org_total_repos.csv	Total repos owned by organizations per country
org_total_stars.csv	Stars (engagement/popularity) of orgs per country
org_total_forks.csv	Total forks by organizations per country
org_total_watchers.csv	Total watchers on org repos per country
contributors_total_repos.csv	Repos owned by individual contributors per country
<i>Organisation level</i>	
org_avg_commits.csv	Average commits per organization
org_avg_followers.csv	Average followers per organization
org_avg_pull_requests.csv	Average pull requests per organization
org_total_commits.csv	Total commits from all orgs
org_total_repos.csv	Total repositories from orgs
org_total_stars.csv	Total stars (engagement proxy)
org_total_forks.csv	Total forks (reuse proxy)
org_total_watchers.csv	Total watchers (interest level)
<i>Repository level</i>	
commits_per_year_repo.csv	Total commits per year by repository
forks_per_year_repo.csv	Total forks per year by repository

stars_per_year_repo.csv

Total stars per year by repository

In Figure 1, some exemplary analyses that are available on the basis of our GitHub indicators are provided. It can be found that the number of repositories as well as organisations have grown over the years until 2020. From then on, however, the numbers are decreasing. This already highlights one general downside of the GitHub indicators, i.e. that it is not obligatory to provide address or country information in the metadata when uploading a GitHub project. This leads to the fact that in only 50% of the cases, country information is available in our data, although we have used a geocoding algorithm to gather as many country level data as possible. This means that for an in-depth analyses of growth rates etc. at the country level, we have to limit our results to repositories where country information is available or we will provide a distorted picture of the OS activities.

Figure 1: Total repositories (upper panel) and organisations (lower panel) created per year and per country

Apart from these more basic indicators, we propose a list of potential further indicators that can be calculated on the basis of our database.

Grouped into four categories these are:

1. Engagement/Popularity

- Total stars given to repos
- Total forks of repos
- Total watchers on repos

2. Contributor Base

- Number of unique contributors by country
- Average public repos per contributor
- Average followers per contributor

3. Repository Ownership

- Number of public repositories (per org, per country)
- Share of repositories that are forks vs. originals
- Average repo size (KB)

4. Activity/Productivity

- Average commits per repository
- Average pull requests per repository
- Contributor-to-repo ratio (as a collaboration index)

Based on these indicators, we are able to provide an assessment of the adoption and the impact of OS activities alongside these four dimensions.

3.1.2 OS innovation indicators

In addition to the OS activity indicators, we have prepared some furthermore classic innovation indicators in order to measure innovation activities in OS. One of these indicators is OS patent filings. Patents can be seen as an output of R&D processes, which at the same time provide an input to future market activities. Especially in technologically relevant markets, patents are the most important visible artefacts of R&D processes and can thus be seen as the most important innovation indicator to assess technological competitiveness at the micro and the macro level (Freeman, 1982; Grupp, 1998). Since patents are one of the most important indicators for (industrial) R&D activity, we have provided a demarcation for OS patents for further analyses, which can also be differentiated by OS hardware and OS software as well as OS hardware and OS software licenses (compare Figure 2 and Figure 3). As can clearly be observed in Figure 2, the number of OS patents is very low. When looking more deeply into the data and differentiating the

patents by OSS and OSH patents (Figure 3), it can further be found that the majority of these patents is categorised as OSH, with field-programmable gate arrays (FGPA) being most prominent. Although these FGPA's often are used in OSH, they are not necessarily limited to it, which further weakens the results. This also makes sense against the background patents and open source rely on two different approaches to sharing and protection, i.e. patents are designed to exclude third parties from usage (for a limited amount of time) whereas the basic idea of open source is the contrary. In sum, this implies that patents are not really suitable as a direct open-source metric. However, the indicator can be used to assess how open source and especially digital technologies in general sit within the broader innovation landscape. Furthermore, they can be used to assess the innovativeness of countries and organisations and can thus serve as a validation measure for the OS activity indicators, being able to help answering the questions, which of the OS activity indicators actually measure OS innovation.

Figure 2: Number and shares of OS patent filings

Figure 3: Shares of OS patents by type in all OS patents

Scientific publications are used as indicators of the scientific strength for the assessment of science systems and as early-stage indicators for innovative activities and may offer a perspective on future innovations, based on current scientific and technological strengths. Therefore, we have also provided a demarcation for OS publications for further analyses, which can also be differentiated by OS hardware and OS software as well as OS hardware and OS software licenses (compare Figure 4 and Figure 5). Here, the focus is on publications that have open source as a topic (in a broad sense) and not publications that themselves are published as open access. As can be seen from the Figure 4, the number of OS publications has been rising over the years, implying a growth of OS topics in the scientific world. In Figure 5 it can further be shown that the share of OSS publications is increasing, leading to a decreasing share of OSH publications, although the absolute number of OSH publications has been increasing over the years.

Figure 4: Number and shares of OS publications

Figure 5: Shares of OS publications by type in all OS publications

Finally, we have prepared an indicator that looks at the number of companies within the “open source industry”, based on Crunchbase (Figure 7). Here, we can also look at firm formation, i.e. the number of OS related startups in a given year.

Figure 6: Number of OSS companies by country

3.2 Indicators of Open Source Sustainability

Based on the interviews done in the first iteration of the research, three top aspects emerged when evaluating the need for funding and support measures.

Security of OSS and OSH projects was the most raised concern, as well as area to improve, e.g., in terms of improving security posture, and capabilities for finding, addressing, and managing vulnerabilities. Level of maintenance of OSS and OSH projects was the second concern, e.g., in terms of productivity and robustness in the development and maintenance of the projects. The innovation potential of OSS and OSH projects in terms of its outputs was a third concern, considering new feature development, or planned features of broader value that would otherwise not be implemented.

Considering the top aspects, a number of important high-level indicators for the health and sustainability of OSS and OSH projects has been brought up repeatedly. Below, we highlight each, as well as potential metrics that can reflect each of them.

3.2.1 Prevalence

Prevalence of projects concerns its adoption, use and dependencies, and can be characterised, e.g., with popularity on development and social media platforms, as well as end-user and technical adoption. Current candidate metric include:

- Popularity of projects: Can be reflected in forks, stars, and watchers (Alami et al., 2024). The metric can be computed by summing the number of forks, stars, and watchers for each project, reflecting external interest and engagement.

3.2.2 Activity

Activity in the project considers the productivity in terms of development and community engagement, considering the development activity and efficiency of both maintainers and contributor, as well as social community activity. Current candidate metric include:

- Overall development activity: Technical activity overall by the community, for example, development and technical writing. I.e. including both the development activity and efficiency of both maintainers and contributor. Can be computed by the count of commits of coding files (other than “txt” and “md”).
- Efficiency: The effectiveness and convenience with which an OSS project manages and advances development, such as accepting and evaluating issues and pull-requests. Can be measured through the average time from PR creation to its closure to reflect the project’s operational effectiveness.
- Response time: The time elapsed between when a community member posted a comment/question and when he or she got a reply/response. Computation: We computed the response time by calculating the average time taken for the first comment to appear on an issue across all projects

3.2.3 Robustness

Robustness of projects concerns their dependence on specific individuals and organisations for development, maintenance, and funding to stay sustained. This aspect can be reflected in many ways, e.g., through a project’s knowledge concentration (bus factor vs elephant factor); attrition, retention and turnover of community; or funding sources (GitHub sponsors, corporate sponsorships). Current candidate metric include:

- Retention: The capacity of an OSS community to keep its contributors active in the community for an extended length of time. Can be measured by the annual increase in the number of active contributors (Alami et al., 2024).
- Turnover: The number of contributors and maintainers who depart an OSS community in a given time frame. Can be computed by counting contributors who authored commits but have been inactive for the past six months, showing the rate of contributor departure (Alami et al., 2024).
- Knowledge concentration: Distribution of contributions and expertise to specific persons or groups within an OSS project, usually measured and explained using a community’s bus- or truck factor. The truck factor method (Avelino et al. 2016) can be used to compute the metric, assessing how concentrated the project knowledge is among a few contributors.

3.2.4 Maturity

Maturity of the project in terms of adopting best practice in OSS or OSH development, including choice and use of scaffolding, documentation practices, and technical quality of projects outputs.

Security is especially important, e.g., in terms of practice and history of finding, addressing and managing vulnerabilities. Current candidate metric include:

- Compliance with the Scorecard: Initiative from OpenSSF¹ under the Linux Foundation. Developer collaboratively by a number of companies. Used by some funders as a means for judging security posture and potential improvements.

¹Scripts and methods for calculation available at <https://github.com/ossf/scorecard?tab=readme-ov-file#view-a-projects-score>

4 Discussion and conclusions

This report presents the initial outputs from Tasks 3.2 and 3.3, and first version of deliverable D3.2. The report summarises the methodological approach, indicative findings, and details on future work within the scope of the two tasks. The final version of the deliverable will include the metrics to be derived, along with related policy recommendations. Below, we expand in further detail per task.

4.1 Indicators of Open Source Impact

Since the project started, we have focused heavily on creating databases that allow for an in-depth analysis of OS developments from different dimensions. We are aware of the fact that this cannot cover the complete universe of OS activities. However, with the data at hand, we are able to provide statistical analyses with the aim to generate insights on the OS (innovation) activities on a broader scale. The indicators are available at the organisational level and can easily be aggregated at the country level to allow for macro-level analyses. In the future, we aim to validate our indicators in order to make sure that they actually measure what they aim to measure provide more detailed analyses at the country level.

4.2 Indicators of Open Source Sustainability

The candidate metrics for characterising health and sustainability of OSS and OSH projects are still tentative and only based on an initial analysis and review of the qualitative survey involving 25 interviewees from funding programs and institutions, as well as projects and foundations that have received funding. Still, they provide a foundation and input to the work towards developing the visualisation tool envisaged in T3.4 in the OS Awards.eu project. The thematic analysis of the interviews is still to be finalised, while the second iteration is already under planning with a focus group planned for Saturday the 31st of January of the European Open Source Week.

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6 Annex A – Interview questionnaire

[Context] For our interview record, could you introduce yourself and your role in funding and supporting open source projects within your organisation?

[Selection Process] How does your organisation decide which open source projects to fund or support?

[Selection Criteria] Could you expand what selection criteria you have and which metrics or signals, if any, you use in the selection process?

[Tracking impact] How, if at all, do you track the impact that your funding or support has on the open source projects?

[Reporting impact] What do you report out about the impact of your funding or support? Who do you report to?

[Impact metrics] Which metrics, if any, do you use for reporting your impact?

[Blind-spots] Was there anything I didn't ask about that you think could be important to know for our research?

Do you have any questions for me or the research team?

[Get direction] What would be helpful for you that we could produce from our research?